

1 **Title**

2 Implementing a group-based multi-component early child development intervention
3 through the government health system in rural Bangladesh: a feasibility study
4

5 **Short running title (70 characters):** Multi-component child development
6 intervention by the health system

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44 **Conflict of interest**

45 All authors declare that they have no conflict of interest

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48 **Abstract**

49 Children in low- and middle-income countries face an increased risk of impaired
50 cognitive development due to contaminated environments, poor nutrition, and
51 inadequate responsive stimulation from caregivers. Implementing multi-component,
52 community-level interventions may reduce these risks; however, there is little evidence
53 supporting implementation of these interventions at scale. We assessed the feasibility of
54 implementing a group-based intervention that included responsive stimulation,
55 maternal and child nutrition, water and sanitation, and childhood lead exposure
56 prevention through the government health system in Chatmohar, Bangladesh. After
57 implementation, we conducted 17 in-depth interviews with frontline health service
58 providers and 12 key informant interviews with their supervisors and managers to
59 explore the facilitators and difficulties implementing such a complex program within the
60 health system. Factors facilitating implementation included: high quality training and
61 skill level of providers, support from community members, family, and supervisors,
62 positive relationships between providers and participants, and provision of children’s
63 toys and books free of cost. Difficulties included increased workload of the providers,
64 complicated group-based yet stage-specific delivery where providers had to manage a
65 large group of mother-child dyads representing many different child age-groups at
66 once, and logistics difficulties in providing toys and books through a centralized health
67 system process. Key informants made suggestions to ensure effective government-level
68 scale-up including engaging relevant NGOs as partners, identifying feasible ways to
69 make toys available, and offering providers meaningful even if non-monetary rewards.
70 These findings can be used to shape the design and delivery of multi-component child
71 development interventions to be delivered through the health system.

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75 **Key words:** Government Health System, Multi-component Group-based

76 intervention, responsive stimulation, WASH, lead exposure prevention, maternal and

77 child nutrition

78 **Highlights**

79 ▪ Multi-component child development interventions are feasible and acceptable

80 ▪ Shortage of skilled government personnel requires additional investment

81 ▪ Barriers faced by the health system were modifiable to achieve scalability

82 ▪ Findings can help integrate multi-component interventions into health systems

84

85

86 **Background**

87 In low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) reduced development potential is a
88 risk for 250 million children under 5¹. In South Asia, 4.7 million infants are born every
89 year with low birth weight ², a risk factor for impaired cognitive development ³. Children
90 in LMICs face additional risk factors affecting cognitive development including
91 contaminated environments ⁴, poor nutrition, and lack of stimulating interactions with
92 their caregivers. Children with impaired early childhood growth and cognitive

93 development are less likely to complete school ^{4,5} and more likely to earn less and
94 contribute less to the economy.

95 Although they have been shown to be effective at improving cognitive outcomes,
96 responsive care giving interventions alone are not sufficient to address all the threats to
97 optimal child development ⁶⁻⁸. However, few interventions have been developed to
98 address multiple factors beyond stimulation and nutrition. One approach to address
99 these threats more effectively is to combine multiple interventions into a unified
100 platform, although there is limited evidence to support this claim. Moreover, through
101 integrated programs, governments have the potential to address multiple sustainable
102 development goals at once, although integration may be difficult. Interventions that
103 simultaneously address multiple risk factors have been recommended in WHO
104 guidelines for improving early childhood development ⁹. These multi-component
105 interventions can be delivered in two ways: 1) Combining components into a stand-
106 alone intervention to be delivered by change agents such as community health workers,
107 or 2) Integrating intervention components into the routine delivery of services in the
108 health system. Successful examples of effective integration exist for HIV/AIDS testing
109 and care with family planning ^{10,11} and non-communicable disease care ¹². Leveraging
110 existing resources and service care infrastructure, streamlining service delivery to
111 optimize patient-centered care, and strengthening public-private partnerships of
112 government agencies were all key strategies for integrating HIV care with non-
113 communicable disease care in the health system ¹². Studies that examined integration
114 from the micro (patient-focused) to macro (system-focused) levels recommended
115 delivery using existing protocols and working with communities and health services to
116 ensure that integration is feasible ¹⁰⁻¹².

117 Despite their advantages, practical experience with implementation of multi-
118 component interventions is limited. Integration of multiple interventions delivered

119 within the health system can increase its efficiency or synergy , but the resulting
120 increased complexity may place an excessive burden on health care providers, and
121 overwhelm the intervention participants¹³. Furthermore, integrated interventions require
122 greater attention to training and supervision, which take into account the diversity in
123 training levels and experiences of government health care providers ¹⁴. A group-based
124 delivery format might counterbalance these drawbacks, if it saves the providers' time
125 and group members are able to engage. The government health system of Bangladesh
126 offers several facility- and community-based interventions, such as the Expanded
127 Program on Immunization (EPI), nutrition services with counseling and supplements
128 provision, Integrated Management of Childhood Illnesses, maternal and neonatal health
129 activities and family planning, along with their social and behavioral change
130 communications components ¹⁵. However, the health system has limited experience
131 delivering multi-component intervention services including child development
132 components in a group-format.

133 In Bangladesh, a multi-component child development intervention had been
134 successfully delivered through routine maternal and child health services. In that
135 intervention study, only one additional intervention component (nutrition) was
136 combined with child stimulation, and the intervention was delivered in small groups of 2
137 mother-child dyads. In the current study, we attempted to combine multiple other
138 intervention components, and to deliver them to larger groups of participants. Our
139 research team developed a multi-component intervention by conducting "Research on
140 Integration of Nutrition, Early childhood development, and WASH" (RINEW) through
141 iterative piloting and revision ^{16,17}. We then conducted a cluster randomized trial of
142 RINEW in rural Bangladesh. Female community health workers (CHWs) who had
143 completed secondary school education were hired to deliver the 9-month RINEW
144 intervention ¹⁸. The CHWs held group meetings with pregnant women and mother-child
145 dyads with children <2 years old simultaneously. The RINEW intervention improved

146 child development as effectively as when the same components were delivered by
147 CHWs through individual household visits in other studies ¹⁸.

148 Building on this experience with RINEW, we modified the session content and the
149 delivery mechanism to improve participants' engagement. We then developed RINEW-G
150 to evaluate the integration of the RINEW package into the routine delivery of services in
151 first-level Government health facilities. This study was conducted to explore the
152 feasibility of delivering RINEW-G along with the existing responsibilities and work
153 schedules of government front line health workers, to pregnant women and lactating
154 mothers of their catchment area, to identify the facilitators and difficulties, and to
155 formulate suggestions for future scale up.

156 **Methods**

157 **RINEW-G intervention**

158 RINEW-G included responsive stimulation, nutrition, water, sanitation and
159 hygiene, maternal mental health, and lead exposure prevention. Frontline government
160 health service providers (providers) delivered the content to groups of intervention
161 participants, sharing images and videos from a tablet, and aided by picture books and
162 health cards (Image 1). Providers also provided participants with enabling commodities
163 such as age-appropriate toys, picture books, micro-nutrient powder for children >6
164 months, food group posters, and kangaroo mother care kits when indicated.

165 [Insert Image 1 Here]

166 The RINEW-G project was jointly implemented by the Ministry of Health and Family
167 Welfare (MoHFW) of the Government of Bangladesh (GoB) and icddr, b in Chatmohar, a
168 rural sub-district of Pabna district in west central Bangladesh. Provider training was six
169 days long and was comprehensive, utilizing audio-visual training materials, such as
170 video clips demonstrating breastfeeding positioning, a poster with different food group

171 pictures, a scenario-based field-test, practical sessions with tablet computers, and
172 supportive supervision. There was on-going supervision throughout the implementation
173 period where supervisors from GoB visited each provider once a month. Supervisors
174 from icddr,b rotated observing each provider's sessions and paid more visits to those
175 providers in need of improvement, to give them on-the-job training. Intervention
176 activities were implemented from August-2019 to March 2020 when nation-wide
177 lockdowns began due to COVID-19 pandemic. The intervention sessions were provided
178 by 71 providers in first-level health care facilities: a) community clinics, b) union health
179 & family welfare centers, c) union sub centers/rural dispensaries, and d) sub-district
180 health complexes (Figure 1). Among these, 57 were main providers, and 14 were back-
181 up providers if main providers were off-duty. Each main provider organized 10-15
182 groups with 10 to 15 participants in each group. The providers (midwives and Family
183 Welfare Visitors) of the pregnant women in their 3rd trimester offered the RINEW-G
184 package at their health facilities. They offered four sessions per group delivered once a
185 month, integrated with the existing four ante-natal care (ANC) visits suggested by best
186 practice following WHO recommendations¹⁹. The providers of the mothers and children
187 up to 24 months old (Sub Assistant Community Medical Officers, senior staff nurses, and
188 Community Health Care Providers) offered 24 sessions per group in the community
189 clinics: 12 main and 12 follow-up sessions with sessions alternating and delivered
190 offered every 2 weeks (Figure 1). Each session covered responsive stimulation and at
191 least one other intervention component. Enabling commodities corresponding to each
192 session were provided to the participants in all sessions. The follow-up sessions were
193 shorter and recapitulated the previous session.

194 [Insert Figure 1 Here]

195 To enroll participants, Family Welfare Assistants visited pregnant women in their
196 third trimester and mothers of children under 12 months of age in their work

197 jurisdiction, explained the project benefits, distributed the RINEW-G health card
198 describing the session topics, and advised contacting a nearby participating health
199 facility, taking along the health card. Upon giving consent at the health facility, providers
200 invited the RINEW-G participants to the sessions by phone call before each session and
201 the Family Welfare Assistants reminded them two to three days prior, visiting their
202 homes.

203 **Sample size and sampling**

204 In February 2020 we studied 29 participants: 17 frontline health service main
205 providers, eight managers, and four supervisors (Table1). The providers were chosen
206 based on their performance quality in about equal numbers of higher and lower
207 performing providers. The managers and supervisors were chosen based on high
208 engagement in RINEW-G and their representing a variety of RINEW-G catchment areas.
209 We included managers at both national and sub-district levels who were responsible for
210 program management, planning, monitoring, and guiding RINEW-G implementation
211 activities. The supervisors were from both MoHFW and icddr,b and responsible for
212 supporting field planning, supervising the providers including on-the-job training,
213 monitoring, and reporting to the managers at the sub-district level (Table 1).

214 [Insert Table 1 Here]

215 **Data collection and analysis**

216 We conducted qualitative assessments in the form of 17 in-depth interviews with
217 the providers and 12 key informant interviews with the managers and supervisors.
218 These were conducted by researchers from icddr,b with several years of qualitative
219 research experience. The semi-structured interview guides included items related to
220 feasibility such as:

- 221 • How have you combined your RINEW-G responsibilities with your existing job
222 responsibilities? What was challenging or easy about it? Why?

- 223 • How well have you been supported in your current job? How good or bad was
224 the support that you received in implementing RINEW-G?
- 225 • [for supervisors] How do you motivate the providers to fulfill their job
226 responsibilities? What type of motivation do you think works best? Why?
- 227 • [For supervisors and providers] What did you think of the training that icddr,b
228 facilitated for the providers in order to implement RINEW-G? What did you like
229 about the training? What needs improvement?

230 The researchers met regularly during the data collection period to discuss data
231 collection progress and ways to overcome any difficulties in the field. All the interviews
232 were recorded using digital audio recorders. The duration of each interview ranged from
233 45-90 minutes. After data collection was complete, the researchers summarized and
234 translated from the audio recordings directly while holding regular meetings to discuss
235 the best way to convey the meaning in English. They compiled interview summaries
236 according to the category of the participants: providers of pregnant women’s groups,
237 providers of mother-baby groups, managers, and supervisors. Then, they coded all
238 summarized data by applying both deductive codes (generated before analysis based
239 on study objectives as illustrated in the qualitative tools) and inductive codes (newly
240 emerged codes identified as coding proceeded).

241 Throughout the data collection and analysis process, we conducted member
242 checking as a measure of trustworthiness ²⁰. We presented and discussed preliminary
243 findings with providers, supervisors and sub-district level managers during their
244 regular monthly meetings in the Upazila Health Complex. The entire data analysis
245 process was completed manually.

246 **Ethical considerations**

247 Interviewers read the full consent form to the participants, and verbal and written
248 consent were obtained prior to the interview and recording. The protocol was approved

249 by the Institutional Review Board at icddr,b (PR-18097), and by the Center for the
250 Protection of Human Subjects at the University of California, Berkeley (2018-12-11673)

251 **Findings**

252 **Socio-demographic characteristics of the participants**

253 Of the 29 participants, 19 had completed over 14 years of formal education including
254 seven medical doctors, two midwives and one nurse. All the managers and supervisors
255 had more than 10 years of work experience (Table 2).

256 [Insert Table 2 Here]

257 **Factors that positively influenced implementation activities**

258 **Prior government-provided training**

259 Providers shared that they had received a high quality three-month training
260 course both from the GoB and from icddr,b prior to RINEW-G. on their regular roles and
261 responsibilities. The training course included: basic knowledge of primary health care,
262 maintenance of health care facilities, and communication with the community they
263 served. The course was residential, five days a week, held from 9am to 5pm. All
264 providers mentioned that whenever any new task had been assigned to them, they had
265 received specific training on that topic, such as training on vaccinations, maternal and
266 child nutrition, and family planning. Some of these trainings were residential, and some
267 were day-long; some were held outside the sub-district.

268 **RINEW-G training and field test**

269 All providers had positive feedback on the RINEW-G-specific training sessions.
270 They said that the training facilitators utilized language that was easy to understand,
271 and were polite and supportive towards them. Providers also had positive comments on
272 the social and behavioral change communication materials and the toys designed for

273 the intervention participants. They said that discussions, role play, and field practices
274 were effective parts of their training. A male mother-baby provider aged 34 explained:

275 *Every training session has some common thing [theme]; RINEW-G also had pre and*
276 *post-test, role play etc. We also have those in government training. But there was*
277 *no field test as RINEW-G had, which was very effective.*

278 Many mother-baby group providers mentioned that what they appreciated the
279 most were the field tests where they worked through real scenarios, because these were
280 helpful and motivating. Most pregnancy group providers made similar statements.
281 Furthermore, the providers said that they were not used to providing group sessions,
282 and they appreciated the group-specific training.

283 **RINEW-G tablet training sessions**

284 All providers asserted that they were trained to distribute the RINEW-G enabling
285 commodities in a timely manner, aided by tablet computers. They learned to use tablet
286 computers to also show respective images and videos to the participants during the
287 sessions. All providers reported that this was useful as they did not need to learn
288 anything by heart.

289 Some providers rated the tablet training as excellent, but the lack of familiarity and
290 practice with handling digital devices made it difficult for others. Some mother-baby
291 providers observed that it was easier and faster for those with previous experience using
292 tablet computers; younger providers had prior experience with handling smart devices
293 like mobile phones and were good at tablet training. One male provider of mother-baby
294 sessions, aged 28 explained:

295 *Most of the men are habituated with smartphone but some of them especially older*
296 *females are not oriented about this digital device as they did not use it ever. I like*
297 *the tablet as whole session is installed here. I can show images; I can save those.*

298 *There are some videos in the tab. When I show those, mothers watch very*
299 *attentively.*

300 Although some of the providers struggled with learning to use tablets, the supervisors
301 said that RINEW-G training in the end enabled all providers to effectively share RINEW-
302 G content with their groups. Furthermore, all providers were able to successfully send
303 session data to the server in a timely manner.

304 **Supervision**

305 All providers felt that they received supportive supervision throughout the
306 RINEW-G training and intervention delivery. One male supervisor from icddr,b, aged 42,
307 said:

308 *All health service providers were supposed to attend a monthly meeting in the UHC*
309 *(sub-district health complex), where the providers submitted their monthly reports*
310 *to their supervisors and discussed various issues related to their regular job. When*
311 *RINEW-G started, each month one official from icddr,b was present in the meeting*
312 *and discussed problems and probable solutions for implementing RINEW-G. This*
313 *happened on a regular basis.*

314 The providers also mentioned receiving health cards and enabling commodities
315 on time from their supervisors, allowing for their timely use and distribution. To facilitate
316 the transport of the commodities from the sub-district health complex to their assigned
317 facilities each month, RINEW-G covered the providers' round-trip transportation costs.
318 One male supervisor, aged 52, from the government reported:

319 *We distributed a bag/box containing toys, picture books and puzzles to the*
320 *providers in the monthly meeting. As they receive money for transportation, they*
321 *never considered it as a problem. Even if they were absent from the meeting, they*
322 *collected the box/bag on another day. If they had not received the transportation*

323 *cost, they wouldn't have collected it on time, and the RINew-G session might have*
324 *been interrupted.*

325 **Family support**

326 All supervisors and providers reported receiving full support from their family
327 members, primarily parents, husbands, wives, elder siblings, and in-laws, to conduct
328 their jobs. Parents and in-laws of the providers looked after the children until the
329 providers returned home. One male mother-baby session provider, aged 34, further
330 explained:

331 *I live with my parents. My wife is a Community Health Care Provider in nearby*
332 *community clinic. We have a 4-year-old boy. My parents look after him and drop*
333 *him at school. My wife prepares food early in the morning and then we both start*
334 *for our workplace. I drop my wife to her workplace first and then come to my own*
335 *workplace. My wife picks my son up from school on her way to home. I must leave*
336 *early as I drop my wife first. Thus, we help each other.*

337 **Community support**

338 All providers reported that they mostly received positive responses from
339 community residents who heed their suggestions and are patient when the facility is
340 very crowded. One, family welfare visitor, aged 54, who provided pregnancy sessions
341 said:

342 *People respect me as doctor. They come to me whenever they get sick and follow*
343 *my suggestions. Children, elderly persons, pregnant women all of them respect me.*
344 *If sometimes I need anything like drinking water, if I told anyone, they give me*
345 *from their house. If I call someone for any task, people come to me and extend their*
346 *helping hands towards me.*

347 Another male mother-baby session provider aged 31 added:

348 *People of this area, respect me as a doctor. Despite being from nonmedical*
349 *background, I get this honor. In that case I will say people help me and honor my*
350 *job. Now I am satisfied with this.*

351 A few providers mentioned that sometimes patients are not cooperative. When
352 there is a long queue, or when medicines are out of stock, patients can get agitated and
353 complain. Sometimes, patients also use offensive words which make the providers lose
354 their motivation to work. One female community health care provider, aged 35, who
355 provided mother-baby sessions, stated:

356 *Some people do not listen to me and use bad words with me. They used to tell that*
357 *we sell the medicine in the market and tell lies to them, saying that medicines are*
358 *finished. On that time, I feel very disheartened, sometimes sit idly, and stop working*
359 *altogether.*

360 Furthermore, two supervisors acknowledged that sometimes it can be difficult for
361 the providers to handle difficult patients. In these cases, the latter should refrain from
362 negative confrontations with patients. Instead, supervisors motivated the providers to
363 have discussions with community groups and ask for the support of elite community
364 members in order to mitigate the problems.

365 **Previous experience on RINEW-G topics and RINEW-G Innovations**

366 All providers and supervisors reported previous familiarity with several of the
367 RINEW-G components such as WASH and maternal and child nutrition. There were new
368 topics such as prevention of lead exposure and child stimulation. All components were
369 delivered through group format, using visual aids and interactive discussions with the
370 participants. One high performing female family welfare visitor, aged 54, who provided
371 pregnancy sessions mentioned:

372 *We are working to provide health services to the community. It includes*
373 *services to the pregnant mothers as well as services to the mother and child.*

374 *We also work for maternal and child nutrition. So much of the RINEW-G*
375 *content is similar to our work. It made our job easier.*

376 However, some topics were new to the providers. One male supervisor, aged 58,
377 explained:

378 *The new thing I found here is lead poisoning and child stimulation. As our*
379 *providers are well trained from the study team and they had previous*
380 *experiences too, they can easily work on the new topics.*

381 Another family welfare visitor, aged 54, pointed out the innovation of group
382 sessions:

383 *We tell mothers what to eat during pregnancy, how to maintain hygiene,*
384 *when to come for check-up, where to go if there is any complication, what is*
385 *the danger sign during pregnancy etc. The only difference is the health*
386 *education we provided earlier was not as organized as we are doing for*
387 *RINEW-G. Earlier we gave health education one to one, now we are doing this*
388 *in groups.*

389

390 **Provider-receiver relationship**

391 All providers reported that they have positive relationships with the RINEW-G
392 mothers. A few felt that they were initially over-qualified in comparison to the
393 requirements of their regular jobs and not happy as a result. However, later,
394 because of RINEW-G , providers were able to build a trustworthy rapport with the
395 community residents and earn their respect, and this counterbalanced their feeling
396 of over-qualification. Most other providers reported that they felt privileged to be
397 able to provide health services to community residents, and they are respected

398 because they are in a job related to health services even though they did not have
399 formal training in health.

400 All providers reported that community residents cooperated with them
401 during organization of RINEW-G activities. Due to their longer interaction with the
402 mothers and children in the group format of RINEW-G, there were some significant
403 changes in the relationships between providers and mothers. Previously, mothers
404 came to the clinic and immediately returned home after receiving medicines from
405 the providers after a short individual interaction. Now, they were interacting with
406 the provider longer for many different types of issues, gathering together as a
407 group, and receiving several material benefits beyond medicines. This improved the
408 relationship between mothers and providers. Due to their close and longer
409 interactions, mothers shared their problems, and sought suggestions from them. As
410 a result, they started considering the providers as family members/relatives . Half of
411 the providers also mentioned their increased closeness with the mothers because of
412 the providers' engaging in play activities with the children as part of RINEW-G. One
413 male provider, aged 32, who provided sessions to mother-baby dyads, mentioned:

414 *Usually, when you talk to mother about her children, mothers become happy, and*
415 *you can build good relationship with them. As I am a Community Health Care*
416 *Provider (CHCP) of this area, and treating people, I already had a good relationship*
417 *with them, and it helped me to conduct group sessions for RINEW-G.*

418 **Difficulties and mitigation strategies**

419 **Providers' workload**

420 RINEW-G activities were additional responsibilities that the providers had to
421 manage on top of their existing tasks. Providers of both pregnancy and mother-baby
422 groups reported that they had to balance heavy workloads. They were already

423 overburdened from carrying out the tasks associated with their full-time clinical jobs. At
424 least once a week, they also needed to travel for various reasons such as attending
425 monthly meetings, receiving their salaries, submitting reports, or observing national or
426 international health-related events as health authority representatives, e.g., “World
427 diabetes day” or “World Day for safe breast-feeding”. Some Family Welfare Visitors and
428 Community Health Care Providers had to travel and serve at the EPI and satellite clinics
429 which are freestanding outpatient service facilities physically separate from but
430 administratively attached to a parent medical facility. Most of the providers reported
431 that initially, more community participants enrolled themselves for RINEW-G sessions
432 than they could attend, compared to normal ANC and well-baby visits. As a result,
433 providers were overwhelmed managing large numbers of groups. Besides, midwives
434 reported that their clinics were understaffed. A midwife aged 26, provider of pregnancy
435 sessions, stated:

436 *Our manpower has reduced, but not the tasks. Earlier for all those tasks we*
437 *were 4, and even then, faced problems, now we are 3 and the work remains*
438 *the same; you can understand how much workload now we have.*

439 National level managers agreed that their providers were already overcommitted.
440 One such male manager, aged 53, said:

441 *When the idea of community clinics was established, it was told that a health*
442 *assistant will be there to assist the CHCP, but it did not happen in reality. CHCPs*
443 *had to do all tasks by themselves. If any new task comes for them, they will*
444 *definitely consider it as a burden.*

445 To mitigate the workload, the RINEW-G study team visited each of the health
446 facilities and suggested merging groups if there were no more than three participants in
447 a single group, due to subsequent stabilization in participation numbers. Thus, the
448 number of groups was reduced, and providers had fewer sessions to conduct.

449 National level managers also mentioned that a lack of motivation was affecting
450 providers with advanced qualifications and those close to retirement age. Hence, those
451 were not eager to receive any new responsibilities.

452 A national level male manager, aged 54, mentioned:

453 *A number of the providers will go to retirement within the next couple of months.*
454 *Considering their older age, we do not expect that they will be willing to learn any*
455 *new topic or any new technology. There was lack of motivation in those cases.*

456 Managers also identified that providers did not receive any reward for their additional
457 work. Moreover, bureaucratic complexities which caused providers to remain in the
458 same position for long periods of time demoralized them.

459 **Health sector infrastructure**

460 Providers mentioned that poor infrastructure in the health sector was another
461 challenge to implementing RINEW-G. Except for some Union Health and Family Welfare
462 Centers, most of the health care centers lacked space for adequate seating, a
463 functioning toilet, drinking water and ventilation. Some providers stated that mothers
464 and their babies suffered a lot during meetings in the summer due to lack of electricity
465 and fans. One female mother-baby session provider, aged 30 said:

466 *Children started crying due to [being too] hot and it became very difficult to*
467 *continue [the] session because of noise. Mothers become busy pacifying their*
468 *children and cannot focus[on] what I am saying.*

469 One community clinic was housed in a very old and damaged building that people
470 were hesitant to remain inside. As a result, the provider conducted RINEW-G sessions
471 outside the building in the open air.

472 RINEW-G commodity storage was a challenge. Due to the large volumes
473 involved, it was not possible to store the commodities at the government warehouse. All

474 providers and their supervisors reported that the commodities could not be stored out
475 in the open as they could be damaged by heat and humidity. To address this problem,
476 icddr,b rented a room and ensured safe/appropriate storage of all the enabling
477 commodities. Icddr,b also provided the cost to transport these commodities to each of
478 the facilities where sessions were conducted.

479 Lastly, toy-making capacity posed another difficulty. An icddr,b male supervisor, aged 42
480 mentioned:

481 *Not only storing or distribution, but also procurement and production of*
482 *stimulation toys are challenging. Most of the stimulation toys are made of*
483 *unnecessary or extra household materials e.g., old fabric, plastic bottles, bangles,*
484 *pipes. A large number of necessary items need time to be gathered. And it is*
485 *found difficult to manage/recruit toy makers.*

486 **Lack of coordination among various government health sector wings**

487 National level managers from icddr,b and the government health system pointed
488 out that Directorate General of Health Services (DGHS) and Directorate General of
489 Family Planning (DGFP) are two distinctive wings of the government health system; that
490 they work separately on recruitment of human resources, monitoring, commodity supply
491 and distribution, and trainings; and that they even have separate budgets and funding
492 (Figure 2). Community clinics and family welfare centers are run by both wings
493 simultaneously, but there is inadequate coordination between them. As a result, there
494 are challenges for RINEW-G training, commodities distribution, and other logistics. A
495 male manager, aged 54, from the government commented:

496 *If it is an integrated [i.e., combined] program then no one thinks it is their own. This*
497 *creates a crisis of ownership.*

498 One strategy used to address this lack of coordination during the feasibility study was
499 engaging one dedicated person from the RINEW-G project, to maintain communication
500 with all departments/divisions/wings of the government health system.

501 **Suggestions and recommendations for future scale-up**

502 **Motivating the health service providers**

503 National level managers suggested that local level managers provide feedback or praise
504 the performance of the providers. The reward could be non-monetary: verbal praise
505 could work as motivation, and managers could give providers certificates of good
506 performance. Although the GoB has no financial reward for the providers, local
507 managers may have funds they could use to arrange rewards for the providers such as
508 encouragement to take part in government-offered online courses and earn a
509 certificate. One national-level male manager aged 52, clarified during an interview:

510 *They [the providers] become frustrated if any new task is assigned. When they get*
511 *bored working in the field, we arrange training for them, praise them, so that they*
512 *regain their enthusiasm. This can be possible when everyone performs his/her*
513 *assigned duty properly, it is a team work, no one alone can do this.*

514 **Identifying a feasible way to distributing RINEW-G enabling commodities**

515 National level managers said that the two separate logistics distribution chains
516 (Figure 2), can be maintained for scaling up distribution of the nutritional supplements.
517 However, they said that the RINEW-G intervention includes child stimulation toys and
518 other new intervention commodities not included in existing logistics systems of both
519 DGHS and DGFP. Therefore, instead of incorporating them into the existing logistics
520 system, managers suggested providing training to the mothers on making child
521 stimulation toys with available materials at home rather than delivering pre-made toys
522 directly to the mothers through two complex and not-well coordinated systems.

523 [Insert Figure 2 Here]

524 This would save cost and time for making and storing toys. A male manager from the
525 government aged 44 said:

526 *During scale up, you should tell the mothers to make the toys and bring those. This*
527 *will create ownership among them. The government will never make and supply*
528 *those.*

529 Moreover, icddr,b managers also reported that the government health system will need
530 technical assistance from partner organizations to address the distribution mechanism
531 and funding for commodities, given the large number of commodities required.

532 **Discussion**

533 The study highlighted facilitators in integrating a group-based multi-component
534 early child stimulation intervention with the government health system in
535 Bangladesh, as well as suggestions on how to overcome challenges for a future
536 scale up (Table 3). The facilitators of the current government health care system
537 included health care staff having high training quality with field-based training,
538 supportive supervision, infrastructures, established network in the communities and
539 the existing support of family and community.

540 [Insert Table 3 Here]

541 The responsive stimulation components of RINEW-G further strengthened the
542 relationships between providers and mothers in the community. Integrated service
543 delivery was easier because RINEW-G covered nutrition education and hygiene
544 practices similar to those in the existing government health care curriculum, while
545 adding responsive stimulation, maternal mental health, and lead exposure
546 prevention. Though lead exposure prevention was a very new topic for them,
547 detailed and hands-on training on this topic, use of easy language and visual aids to
548 explain the potential exposure sources, toxic effects of lead, and preventive

549 measures facilitated their delivery of the material. Additionally, experiences from the
550 preceding phase of the RINEW project informed revision of the contents and
551 definition of the delivery mechanism of RINEW-G. Group format delivery was a
552 facilitator in that it saved time and could reach more people compared to individual
553 facility-based consultations and home visits, but also a challenge because of the
554 difficulties in managing large groups.

555 The combination of many intervention components increased workload for the
556 providers. There was lack of motivation by older providers to engage with digital
557 technologies, poor infrastructure of the health care facilities, and lack of
558 coordination among different wings of the government health system of
559 Bangladesh. The recommendations made by national level managers identified non-
560 monetary motivation strategies for the providers, as well as collaboration with
561 partner organizations and financial donors to enhance future scale up opportunities.

562 The study findings emphasized that the capacity building process benefited from
563 the training the health workers had previously received to provide services in the
564 government health facilities. Our findings are aligned with other studies where prior
565 experience in health care services improved skills to deliver early childhood
566 development interventions ²¹. The findings on strong interpersonal relationships
567 between the health service providers, family members, and community residents which
568 aided in building trust in the recommended intervention agree with an earlier review
569 which underlined the importance of client-provider relationship in health care service
570 programs to address the needs of the people ²².

571 It is well recognized that Bangladesh has a chronic shortage of trained health
572 care workforce ²³. The relationship between the workload and performance has been
573 widely acknowledged. Health professionals' perceptions of their workload were shown
574 to be influenced by work interruptions and work-related uncertainties, and perception

575 of a moderate level of workload was associated with improved performance ^{24,25}. Other
576 studies have presented a similar recommendation that ensuring smooth workflow and
577 minimizing unnecessary work interruptions ²⁴, could support implementation of
578 integrated early child development and nutrition interventions delivered through the
579 health system.

580 Acknowledging the workload implications of individual home visits or one-to-one
581 counseling as the standard of practice, and focusing on designing a potentially scalable
582 intervention, we designed the intervention curriculum to be delivered in group format in
583 RINEW-G. A group format delivery might eventually reduce the providers' workload,
584 upon mastering the material, as well as improve RINEW-G's scalability. However, the
585 group session format called for better facility infrastructure, with better seating and
586 better sanitation, in order to handle many non-toilet-trained babies at a time for longer
587 time periods, compared to an individual session format. This problem remained
588 unresolved in the older facilities which lacked such amenities and presents an important
589 barrier to scalability of RINEW-G. Substantial investment would be required for
590 infrastructure improvements of the clinic buildings for consistently hosting group
591 sessions without interruptions.

592 Regarding the reported lack of motivation of providers to assume responsibility
593 for additional tasks, strategies to strengthen workforce motivation such as forms of
594 praise and recognition, whether monetary or not, can be added. According to the
595 managers and supervisors, solutions appropriate for low-resource settings like rural
596 Bangladesh should incorporate non-monetary incentives to adequately motivate the
597 government health care providers. One study identified motivation as one of the key
598 factors influencing work performance and a significant predictor of resignation from a
599 workplace ²⁶. Incentives both monetary and non-monetary can play a significant role to
600 motivate and improve work performance ^{27,28}.

601 Government health centers in Bangladesh have limited space ²³, which is
602 unfavorable for storing enabling commodities required in any intervention. Therefore,
603 we agree that distribution of bulky enabling commodities by the government needs
604 careful consideration. Hands-on training followed by the construction of age-
605 appropriate toys for child development by the children's families might make scalability
606 more feasible. Collaboration with local organizations to store and distribute other
607 commodities can be a second strategy to support management and distribution of a
608 large number of commodities to community members.

609 Furthermore, the multi-component intervention calls for collaboration with
610 national and international private organizations specializing in the respective
611 components. Collaboration may also help during the transition to scale up in training,
612 developing, and printing behavioural change communication materials and other
613 technical support with their expertise. Local partners and community agencies were
614 recognized as supportive during the transition to scale and in mitigating challenges of
615 child development interventions ²⁹.

616 Regarding lack of coordination among multiple wings within the government
617 health sector and the local higher authorities, earlier studies have found that the extent
618 of integration can be influenced by the desirability and commitment of the national
619 leaders to successful integration of a program into primary health care ³⁰. Conversely,
620 lack of government commitment contributed to poor integration of a childhood illness
621 management program, for example, in Peru ³¹. For maximum effectiveness and mass
622 coverage, it is important that government policy makers understand the interrelated
623 components of the multicomponent intervention and adapt a multisectoral
624 comprehensive approach bringing different health care wings under the same umbrella.
625

626 An important limitation was the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on
627 intervention delivery, due to the countrywide lockdown that started in March 2020. This
628 resulted in the premature ending of the intervention delivery and the interruption of
629 data collection afterwards. The pandemic also affected the original plan of conducting
630 qualitative interviews at the midpoint of the intervention. However, we were able to
631 implement all sessions for the pregnant women group and two thirds of the mother-
632 baby sessions. Lastly, RINEW-G as a demonstration project¹⁸ was implemented in a small
633 geographic area which limits the generalizability of the findings regarding a future scale
634 up. However, the findings contribute to the ongoing learning platform to strengthen the
635 maternal and child health care services at the national level.

636 **Conclusion**

637 A responsive stimulation, WASH, lead exposure prevention, maternal and child
638 nutrition, and maternal mental health intervention delivered to groups was feasible and
639 acceptable by implementing government health service providers in Bangladesh. The
640 barriers faced by the health system were modifiable, therefore scalability seems
641 achievable. Nevertheless, the clear shortage of skilled government personnel and the
642 small size of some government healthcare facilities means that taking these additional
643 tasks on would require additional investment by the Government of Bangladesh. The
644 government would need to consider whether this would be a good use of scarce
645 resources or whether those resources would be better deployed towards another
646 activity. Implementing RINEW-G through the government health system with
647 engagement of other relevant organizations can be an effective solution to improve
648 child development outcomes in Bangladesh. Our findings can be used more generally to
649 shape integrated interventions to be delivered through health systems to improve child
650 development.

651 **References**

- 652 1. Black MM, Walker SP, Fernald LC, et al. Advancing Early Childhood Development: From Science to
653 Scale 1: Early childhood development coming of age: Science through the life course. *Lancet (London,*
654 *England)*. 2017;389(10064):77.
- 655 2. Upadhyay RP, Naik G, Choudhary TS, et al. Cognitive and motor outcomes in children born low
656 birth weight: a systematic review and meta-analysis of studies from South Asia. *BMC pediatrics*.
657 2019;19(1):1-15.
- 658 3. Akhtar S. Malnutrition in South Asia—a critical reappraisal. *Critical reviews in food science and*
659 *nutrition*. 2016;56(14):2320-2330.
- 660 4. Lin A, Arnold BF, Afreen S, et al. Household environmental conditions are associated with
661 enteropathy and impaired growth in rural Bangladesh. *The American journal of tropical medicine and*
662 *hygiene*. 2013;89(1):130-137.
- 663 5. Grantham-McGregor S, Cheung YB, Cueto S, et al. Developmental potential in the first 5 years for
664 children in developing countries. *The lancet*. 2007;369(9555):60-70.
- 665 6. Aboud FE, Yousafzai AK. Global health and development in early childhood. *Annu Rev Psychol*.
666 2015;66(1):433-457.
- 667 7. Hamadani JD, Nahar B, Huda SN, Tofail F. Integrating early child development programs into
668 health and nutrition services in Bangladesh: benefits and challenges. *Annals of the New York Academy of*
669 *Sciences*. 2014;1308(1):192-203.
- 670 8. Larson LM, Yousafzai AK. A meta-analysis of nutrition interventions on mental development of
671 children under-two in low-and middle-income countries. *Maternal & child nutrition*. 2017;13(1):e12229.
- 672 9. Organization WH. *Improving early childhood development: WHO guideline*. World Health
673 Organization; 2020.
- 674 10. Lindegren ML, Kennedy CE, Bain-Brickley D, et al. Integration of HIV/AIDS services with maternal,
675 neonatal and child health, nutrition, and family planning services. *Cochrane Database of Systematic*
676 *Reviews*. 2012;(9)
- 677 11. Narasimhan M, Yeh PT, Haberlen S, Warren CE, Kennedy CE. Integration of HIV testing services
678 into family planning services: a systematic. 2019;
- 679 12. Njuguna B, Vorkoper S, Patel P, et al. Models of integration of HIV and noncommunicable disease
680 care in sub-Saharan Africa: lessons learned and evidence gaps. *AIDS (London, England)*. 2018;32(Suppl
681 1):S33.
- 682 13. Mounier-Jack S, Mayhew SH, Mays N. Integrated care: learning between high-income, and low-
683 and middle-income country health systems. *Health policy and planning*. 2017;32(suppl_4):iv6-iv12.
- 684 14. Munabi-Babigumira S, Glenton C, Lewin S, Fretheim A, Nabudere H. Factors that influence the
685 provision of intrapartum and postnatal care by skilled birth attendants in low-and middle-income
686 countries: a qualitative evidence synthesis. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*. 2017;(11)
- 687 15. Joarder T, Chaudhury TZ, Mannan I. Universal health coverage in Bangladesh: activities,
688 challenges, and suggestions. *Advances in Public Health*. 2019;2019
- 689 16. Jahir T, Winch PJ, Leontsini E, et al. Success Factors for Community Health Workers in
690 Implementing an Integrated Group-Based Child Development Intervention in Rural Bangladesh.
691 *International journal of environmental research and public health*. 2021;18(15):7891.
- 692 17. Yeasmin F, Winch PJ, Hwang ST, et al. Exploration of attendance, active participation, and behavior
693 change in a group-based responsive stimulation, maternal and child health, and nutrition intervention.
694 *The American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*. 2021;104(4):1586.
- 695 18. Pitchik HO, Tofail F, Rahman M, et al. A holistic approach to promoting early child development: a
696 cluster randomised trial of a group-based, multicomponent intervention in rural Bangladesh. *BMJ global*
697 *health*. 2021;6(3):e004307.

- 698 19. WHO. *WHO Recommendations on Antenatal Care for a Positive Pregnancy Experience*. Geneva:
699 *World Health Organization*; . Report. 2016
- 700 20. Krefting L. Rigor in qualitative research: The assessment of trustworthiness. *The American journal*
701 *of occupational therapy*. 1991;45(3):214-222.
- 702 21. Kohli-Lynch M, Hardy VP, Salazar RB, et al. Human resources and curricula content for early child
703 development implementation: multicountry mixed methods evaluation. *BMJ open*. 2020;10(4):e032134.
- 704 22. Dwamena F, Holmes-Rovner M, Gaulden CM, et al. Interventions for providers to promote a
705 patient-centred approach in clinical consultations. *Cochrane database of systematic reviews*. 2012;(12)
- 706 23. Islam A, Biswas T. Health system in Bangladesh: challenges and opportunities. *American Journal of*
707 *Health Research*. 2014;2(6):366-374.
- 708 24. Asamani JA, Amertil NP, Chebere M. The influence of workload levels on performance in a rural
709 hospital. *British Journal of Healthcare Management*. 2015;21(12):577-586.
- 710 25. Shah SSH, Jaffari AR, Aziz J, Ejaz W, UI-Haq I, Raza SN. Workload and performance of employees.
711 *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*. 2011;3(5):256-267.
- 712 26. Zurn P, Dolea C, Stilwell B. *Nurse retention and recruitment: developing a motivated workforce*.
713 International Council of Nurses; 2005.
- 714 27. Abduljawad A, Al-Assaf AF. Incentives for better performance in health care. *Sultan Qaboos*
715 *University Medical Journal*. 2011;11(2):201.
- 716 28. Henderson LN, Tulloch J. Incentives for retaining and motivating health workers in Pacific and
717 Asian countries. *Human resources for health*. 2008;6(1):1-20.
- 718 29. Radner JM, Ferrer MJ, McMahon D, Shankar AH, Silver KL. Practical considerations for
719 transitioning early childhood interventions to scale: lessons from the Saving Brains portfolio. *Annals of the*
720 *New York Academy of Sciences*. 2018;1419(1):230-248.
- 721 30. Kasturiaratchi N, Settinayake S, Grewal P. Processes and challenges: how the Sri Lankan health
722 system managed the integration of leprosy services. *Leprosy review*. 2002;73(2):177-185.
- 723 31. Huicho L, Dávila M, Campos M, Drasbek C, Bryce J, Victora CG. Scaling up integrated management
724 of childhood illness to the national level: achievements and challenges in Peru. *Health policy and planning*.
725 2005;20(1):14-24.

726

727

Figure 1: Number of facilities and providers who participated in the RINEW-G feasibility study

Figure 2: Commodities/logistics distribution process of Directorate General of Family Planning (DGFP) and Directorate General of Health Services (DGHS)

Image 1: RINEW-G training materials

Way to stay healthy

- ✓ Wash hands with soapy water on recommended times
- ✓ Ensure feces free environment by safe disposal of feces & using sanitary latrine
- ✓ Ensure safely preserved food and arsenic free drinking water
- ✓ Ensure lead contamination free food

- ✓ Feed your child adequate food from at least five food groups every day and take adequate food from all 10 food groups every week.
- ✓ Breastfeed exclusively for 6 months and continue breastfeeding up to 2 years with complementary food.
- ✓ Feed your child homemade food instead of chips, biscuits, juice and chocolate etc.

- ✓ Interact with children <2 years -talking & playing during daily activities
- ✓ Hand them age specific toys and picture books
- ✓ Ensure responsive feeding
- ✓ Mothers: Think healthy about your
 - own health
 - relation with children
 - relation with others.

RINEW STUDY

Child card

Mother's ID: _____ Date of Enrollment: _____

Mother's Name: _____

Father/ Husband's Name: _____

Child's Name _____

Date of birth: Day _____ Month _____ Year _____

Address: House/Holding no: _____ Village: _____

Upazila: _____ District: _____

Union: _____ Ward no: _____

Community Clinic: _____

HA/FWA's Name: _____

Mobile Number: _____

Please preserve this card carefully. Bring and show this card to the health care provider in every meeting.

RINEW-G health card for child

Picture books

Pictorial cards age-appropriate toys and puzzles to discuss demonstrate child's gradual development

Table 1: Sample size and sampling

Data type	Total conducted	Category	Participant type	Number of eligible participants	Number of selected participants	Selection criteria
In depth interviews	17	Providers	Community Health Care Promoters (CHCP)	33	10	High and low performers
			Midwives	4	2	
			Sub assistant Community Medical Officer	13	2	
			Family Welfare Visitor	10	2	
			Senior Staff nurse	2	1	Provided most sessions
Key informant interviews	8	Managers from GoB and icddr,b sub-district level	Upazila Health and Family Planning Officer (UH&FPO)	1	1	Posted in that sub-district during implementation and data collection period
			Medical Officer maternal and child health MO-MCH(FP)	1	1	
		Upazila Family Planning Officer (UFPO)	1	1		
		Assistant program manager	1	1		
		Managers from GoB and icddr,b at	Deputy project coordinator	2	1	

Data type	Total conducted	Category	Participant type	Number of eligible participants	Number of selected participants	Selection criteria
		national level				
			National level managers from Directorate General of Health Services (DGHS,) Directorate General of Family Planning (DGFP) and Community Based Health Care (CBHC)	3	3	
	4	Supervisors from GoB and icddr,b	Assistant Family Welfare Officer (AFWO)	1	1	Assigned to RINEW-G
			Health Inspector	2	1	
			Assistant Health Inspector	2	1	
			Field Research Assistant	2	1	

Table 2: Demographic characteristics of study participants

Demographic characteristics	Type of study participants		
	Providers N=17	Managers N=8	Supervisors N=4
Age (Years)			
25-35	13	-	-
36-45	-	3	1
46-55	4	5	1
56-65	-	-	2
Formal education (Years)			
12	4	-	1
14	4	-	1
> 14	9	8	2
<i>Doctor</i>	-	7	-
<i>Midwife</i>	2	-	-
<i>Nurse</i>	1	-	-
Working experience (Years)			
<5	4	-	-
5-10	4	-	-
>10	9	8	4
Sex			
Male	11	7	4
Female	6	1	-

Table 3: Factors influencing implementation of RINEW-G through the government health system of Bangladesh

Influencing factors		
Facilitators	Difficulties	Suggestion to future scale up
1. Health service providers received high quality training	1. Workload of the health service providers and supervisors	1. Implement group-based format
2. Health service providers' appropriate background and previous relevant work experiences	2. Difficulties with using tablet computers especially by the older providers	2. Involve highly experienced health service providers; provide high quality training
3. Similarities between content and delivery pattern of RINEW-G intervention and the government health services	3. Difficulties integrating intervention enabling commodities within the government health system	3. Identify feasible way for distributing commodities such as engaging relevant non-government organizations to support government and teach mothers to make age-appropriate toys on their own
4. Support from family and community to work as health service providers	4. Poor infrastructure of the health service centers and unavailability of water, sanitation, and hygiene facilities	4. Work with the limitations that cannot be easily mitigated; newer health service centers are larger
5. Support from supervisors and RINEW-G study team to continue job responsibilities	5. External factors and lack of motivation of providers	5. Provide various types of rewards to the providers
6. Group facilitation format promises reduction of health service providers' workload in the long term	6. Difficulties managing and conducting sessions with mother-baby group and pregnancy group simultaneously	6. Make the group size smaller (8-10) and separate the two groups